

The Formation of G.P.S Priests!

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Pope Francis, informally addressing the Union of Superior Generals on 29 November 2013, noted that the religious formation today “calls for a different attitude. For example, problems are not solved simply by forbidding doing this or that. Dialogue, as well as confrontation, are needed... Dialogue must be serious, without fear, sincere.... Formation is a work of art, not a police action. We must form their hearts. Otherwise we are creating little monsters. And then these little monsters mold the People of God. This really gives me goose bumps.”¹

True to the above words of Pope Francis, the formation of the seminarians in the Catholic Seminaries today is both a privileged and a demanding task. The formation programme is envisioned to help them become integrated persons for the priestly ministry in the Church. It is envisaged to assist the overall growth of the seminarians with an emphasis on spiritual, human (physical and emotional), intellectual, pastoral and missionary dimensions, so that they go through proper discernment and personal interiorization. The enriching

formation programme also fosters a sense of belongingness, freedom with responsibility, transparency and accountability, punctuality and affective maturity, openness and promptness, morals and faith-based convictions, and empowers them to face the global and local challenges of our day. However, even after such a long period of holistic formation the desired results in the pastoral field or in the missionary front beyond the protective walls of the seminary seem to be discouraging and dissatisfactory.

In my recent conversation with a group of laity concerning the expectations that they have from the present and would-be-clergy, three formative aspects stood out very strongly. They expect a Catholic priest or a Seminarian to be:

1. A God-centred person (G)
2. A People-friendly person (P)
3. A Service-minded person (S)

1. Priest as a God-Centred Person

Today, our faithful seek a priest who is a man of God, living and witnessing God's tenderness and inspires a life of holiness. A God-centered priest through his witnessing life and sanctifying ministry strives to move towards a God-centred existence. The focus of his priestly ministry is 'God' and not 'self'. He is aware that his vocation as a priest is an unconditional gift and not his merit or achievement. In administering and celebrating the sacraments, he shows profound 'devotion' and not merely an external 'performance' of some ostentatious rituals coupled with superficial piety. The faithful entrusted to his care see him praying and being available for their spiritual needs 24X7. They feel the warmth

of a fatherly figure and the tenderness of a good shepherd in him. To the faithful, his spiritual fatherhood models the love of God and others in service. They fear him if he turns out to be a ‘religious nut’, whose insistence on religious duties and obligations demonstrates rigidity and scrupulosity.

The journey to be a God-centred priest begins already in the formation house. In addition to his academic, human and pastoral formation, a seminarian takes his spiritual formation seriously and responsibly. No wonder, “the heart of spiritual formation is personal union with Christ, which is born of, and nourished in, a particular way by prolonged and silent prayer. By prayer, listening to the Word, devout participation in the sacraments, in the liturgy and in community life, the seminarian fortifies his personal union with God after the example of Christ, who had, as his programme of life to do the will of His Father (cf. Jn 4:34).” (*The Gift of the Priestly Vocation* 102). The self-transforming prayer and reflective silence for personal interiorization are the greatest values that he can cultivate in order to discover the spiritual gifts that he is being blessed with, for the priestly life. Regular practice of *Lectio Divina*, daily participation in the Eucharist, praying the Liturgy of the hours, meaningful celebration of the sacrament of Penance, seeking timely spiritual direction are some of the privileged means through which he can attain the goal of his spiritual life, that is to establish a deep union with God. In short, formation for God-centred existence is the foundational dimension in the shaping of the spirituality of a would-be priest.

2. Priest as a People-Friendly Person

The God-centred existence or God-closeness of a priest is clearly manifested in his closeness to the people. Evidently,

the people seek a priest, who is truly human and genuinely compassionate, who has the ability to listen and understand them. What they appreciate the most is their pastor's ability to accompany them, not only in their faith formation but also in their ordinary lives, marked by joys and sorrows, ups and downs, happiness and sorrows. As Pope Francis would say that the true vocation and mission of a priest is to be and to become a "shepherd with the smell of the sheep". Following this analogy, a priest becomes enriched not only by his personal experiences and encounters with the people but also by the experiences of his flock which he brings into the breaking of the Word and its sharing in his homily that truly becomes "the touchstone for judging a pastor's closeness and ability to communicate to his people" (*GPV* 177).

This brings to the fore the human and pastoral formation of the seminarians in our context today. The priestly formation is always permeated by a pastoral spirit. Rightly said, to be pastoral is to be human first, so that we exclude none and include everyone. In this regard, the pastoral formation intends to prepare the seminarians for the *pastoral accompaniment* of children, young people, sick, elderly, disabled, and those who live in situations of isolation and poverty. Accompanied by human formation, it helps them become humanly balanced, serene and stable, valuing inter-personal relationships, so that they become priests with friendly traits, who are authentic, loyal, interiorly free, affectively stable, capable of weaving together peaceful inter-personal relationships and living the evangelical counsels or the promises without rigidity, hypocrisy or loopholes. The desired result is to become experts in the "art of pastoral discernment", that is, the ability to listen deeply to the real situations of the people (*GPV* 120). Further,

the courses on homiletics help them integrate the real-life issues of people with insights from the Word of God than merely communicate some abstract theological ideas that affect neither the preacher nor his faithful. In short, a truly human priest visibly manifests the true and unconditional love of God to people both in words and deeds.

3. Priest as a Service-Minded Person

A priest manifests his God-centredness and Pastoral-closeness through his service. His priestly ministry is based on the conviction that ‘others’ come before the ‘self’. The selfless service of a priest demonstrates that the divine is concretely experienced in the service of the other (Mt 25: 34-40). To a service-minded priest, having ‘no time’ is never an excuse, for he always takes time out of his busy schedule to address the issues that affect his faithful. Today, in many quarters of the church, the faithful complain about their priest regarding his unavailability and the misuse of power and pastoral resources, arrogance and self-righteous attitude, arbitrary and autocratic behaviour based on personal whims and fancies. Regular meetings, cells, associations, and celebrations keep the priest ‘busy’, thus making him more of a ‘functionary’ and his activity more of work devoid of genuine love.

To become a service-minded priest, the formation helps a seminarian to identify what is essential and non-essential. Work makes one tired, but service keeps one joyful, for it is done in the name of the Lord. The weekend-ministries (both social and pastoral), if taken seriously, become a real source of joy, that not only expose the seminarian to the concrete human realities around him but also immerse him to face more challenges boldly. And as a seminarian, if he finds himself happiest when being of service to others, he can be

certain that his future ministry as a priest would be a joyful and sacrificial one in the likeness of Jesus, who “came not to be served but to serve” (Mk 10:45). Therefore, the formation programme assists a seminarian to become a priest who puts the interests of the community before his, more of service-minded, less of power-hungry, more of available and less of busy and more of joyful in ministry and less of depressed, burdened and unhappy.

To conclude, let us wish that the priestly formation in India may truly become an authentic process of shaping God-centred, people-friendly, and service-minded priests (G.P.S), whose holiness of spiritual life, the accompaniment of pastoral life and the humility and simplicity of personal life bring people closer to God.

Notes

1. Antonio Spadaro, “Wake up the World: Conversation with Pope Francis about the Religious Life”, *La Civiltà Cattolica* I (2014), pp. 8-9.